

3. Sustainable Finance: A Case Study of Jsw Steel Ltd

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Abstract

Sustainable financial measures are the dominant requirement of this century. The measures taken by the Indian companies have been significant in recent years, especially after the situation of pandemic, the urgency of sustainable reporting has taken the toll and many Indian corporate firms have been taking steps beyond the governmental regulations towards sustainability. The JSW steel is one of the main leading companies in steel sector and the case study is based on sustainable financial measures taken by the company. The scope of the study is from 2019-19 to 2022-23. Correlation results indicate that environment and governance factors have positive correlation on financials and social factors have negative correlation on financials. The significance value indicates that the Null hypotheses are accepted for all factors. The Durbin Watson test indicates positive autocorrelation of social and governance factors on financials while negative autocorrelation of environment on financials of the company.

Key Words: Sustainable, sustainable finance, finance, ESG.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the parameters followed by the JSW Steel in sustainable finance.
2. To narrate the importance of such parameters with financial analysis.

Review of Literature

Mathew Archer (2019) has pointed out the strategy that enables the investors to keep invested in those companies that are sustainable. The main findings of the study of the author suggested that recent developments in investor behaviour has been observed that suggests the more investment approach towards those companies which are highly sustainable. The social as well as governance related measures are also the one of the consideration taken by the rational investors. **Ali M Fatemi et al. (2013)** narrated that more emphasize on external consideration has affected the environmental and social costs to the company. The authors suggested a sustainable framework for computing social as well as environmental costs. **M. Ziolo et al. (2020)** provided highlights on sustainable finance model in which the authors considered

Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) in focus. The European Countries are the primary criteria for the model and adopted observational study design. **D. Schoenmaker (2018)** pointed out that financial measures can be used to achieve the environmental, social and governance goals. The findings of the study are helpful as it provides the principals of sustainable finance along with empirical data. **Mariam Al Muhairi et al. (2019)** suggested that environment, social and governance factors have greater significant in climate change related investment measures. The authors suggested that planned framework may help to address the climate risks, green house gas emission and other sustainable problems. **Bożena Ryszawska (2016)** author published paper suggesting transition from classical finance approach towards sustainable finance and responsible investing. The author focused on the approach of “F.W.Geels: Multilevel Perspective Model” for sustainable transition. The author found that old system needs to get changed and the idea of sustainable finance should be adopted to meet upcoming environmental challenges. **Y. Danilov (2021)** published a paper suggesting a theoretical framework regarding sustainable finance. The main idea behind the whole study was to focus on “United Nations Model of Environment” and specially on “ESG Framework”. The investment pattern and way of conducting investment approach towards sustainable based concept requires a proper attention.

Introduction

The world has witnessed a major change after the breakdown of pandemic; the financial paradigm has also witnessed the major considerations which includes the sustainable approach. The case study focuses upon the JSW Steel and its sustainable finance practices. The study focuses upon the various approaches taken by the company, as it includes the major areas of sustainability given by national and international environmental committees and Indian government guidelines. The company follows the reporting guidelines given by the “SEBI”. The company is one of the most important players in steel industry in India and across the world. The sustainable finance is the key theme for the study, and the model has been developed by the author keeping the due care for meeting important standards of area of research.

The JSW Steel is a significant player producing more than 25 million tonnes of steel in India as well as United States of America. The company has been promising in the context of sustainability, as it got listed in “Dow Jones Sustainability Index (DJSI)” and also the company had received three consecutive “World Steel Association’s Steel Sustainability Champion Award (2019-2021)”.

Methodology of the Study

Scope of the study

The study is conducted for 5 years from 2018-19 to 2022-23. The sustainable data is collected from the ESG book of the company and financial data is collected from the “Moneycontrol” and “Trendlyne”. All the statistical tests are based upon the net score of the each dimension.

Variables of the Study

Dimension	Parameter	Dependent/Independent	Score Criteria	
Environment	Energy (coal)	Dependent	Decrease	
	Water (specific water consumption)	Dependent	Decrease	
	Waste(Hazardous waste generated)	Dependent	Decrease	
	Emission (scope 1 and 2)	Dependent	Decrease	
	Air Emission	Dependent	Decrease	
Social	Employment (Total Employees)	Dependent	Increase	
	Employees Turnover Rate (%)	Dependent	Decrease	
	Gender Diversity	Dependent	Increase	
	Avg Training Hrs	Dependent	Increase	
	Employees cost	Dependent	Increase	
	Governance	Women	Dependent	Increase
		CSR	Dependent	Increase
Shareholders' complaint (outstanding)		Dependent	Neutral (Resolved at the end of year)	
Whistle Blower		Dependent	Neutral (Resolved at the end of year)	
Meetings (No. Of meetings)		Dependent	Increase	
Financials	ROCE	Independent	Increase	
	Current Ratio	Independent	Increase/Neutral	

	Firm Value	Independent	Increase
	Net Profit (%)	Independent	Increase
	Debt Equity	Independent	Decrease

Hypotheses of the Study

H1: There is a major significance of Environment factors on the Financials of the company.

H2: There is a major significance of Social factors on the Financials of the company.

H3: There is a major significance of Governance factors on the Financials of the company.

Results and Discussion

Sustainable Finance Score table of JSW Steel

Dimension	Parameter	2022-23	2021-22	2020-21	2019-20	2018-19	Score
Environment	Energy	-	✓	✓	-	✓	3
	Water	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	4
	Waste	-	-	✓	✓	✓	3
	Emission	-	-	✓	✓	-	2
	Air Emission	✓	✓	✓	-	-	3
	TOTAL						15
Social	Employment	✓	-	-	✓	-	2
	ETR	-	-	-	✓	-	1
	GEDR	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	4
	AVGTRHRS	✓	✓	-	✓	-	3
	EMPCOST	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	5
	TOTAL						15
Governance	WOMEN	✓	✓	-	-	✓	3
	CSR	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	5
	SHCOMPLAINT	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	5
	WHISTLE	-	-	✓	✓	✓	3
	METTINGS	-	-	✓	-	-	1
	TOTAL						17
Financials	ROCE	-	✓	✓	-	✓	3
	Current Ratio	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	5

	Firm Value	-	✓	✓	-	-	2
	NP	-	✓	✓	-	✓	3
	Debt Equity	-	✓	✓	-	✓	3
	TOTAL						16

Table showing calculations of Pearson Correlation:

Particulars	Environment	Social	Governance	Financials
Environment	1			
Social	-0.447	1		
Governance	0.423	-0.567	1	
Financials	0.645	-0.722	0.218	1

The above table indicates that environment and governance factors are positively correlated with the financials of the company, while social factors have been negatively correlated with the financials of the company.

Table showing results of Regression analysis

Particulars	Environment	Social	Governance
R-Square	.417	.521	.048
P-Value	.239	.169	.724
Durbin Watson	2.655	1.083	1.146

1. Dependent Variable: Environment, Social, Governance
2. Independent Variable: Financials

The above table indicates the data related to regression analysis. The R-Square value indicates 41% impact of environment on financials of the company, 52% impact of social factors on financials of the company and 4.8% impact of governance factors on financials of the company. The p-value suggests that there is no significance of either of the variable on financials of the company. Durbin Watson test suggests that environment factor is having negative autocorrelation on financials of the company, while social and governance factors have positive autocorrelation on financials of the company.

Conclusion

The study provides important highlights on the relation of the sustainable considerations with financial aspects of the company. The study suggested that how environmental, social and governance factors have impact on the financials of the company. The study has its own limitation as the data is secondary in nature; however the reliability is not compromised. The

study is helpful for the academicians, research scholars and institutions as it provides highlights on the sustainable approach with context of finance.

References

- Archer, M. (2019). Sustainable Finance. Environmental Science. <https://doi.org/10.1093/obo/9780199363445-0117>
- Danilov, Y. (2021). Sustainable Finance: a New Theoretical Paradigm. World Economy and International Relations, 65(9), 5–13. <https://doi.org/10.20542/0131-2227-2021-65-9-5-13>
- Fatemi, A. M., & Fooladi, I. (2013). Sustainable finance: A new paradigm. Global Finance Journal, 24(2), 101–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfj.2013.07.006>
- JSW - CSR Stories. (n.d.). JSW. <https://www.jsw.in/foundation/csr-stories>
- Muhairi, M. A., & Nobanee, H. (2019). Sustainable Financial Management. Social Science Research Network. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3472417>
- Ryszawska, B. (2016). Sustainability transition needs sustainable finance. Copernican Journal of Finance & Accounting, 5(1), 185. <https://doi.org/10.12775/cjfa.2016.011>
- Schoenmaker, D. (2018). Principles of sustainable finance. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Principles-of-Sustainable-Finance-Schoenmaker-Schramade/29e61337bca5c8abfb95fcf46c4a9fb5ac861474>
- Steel plant in India – JSW Steel. (n.d.). JSW. <https://www.jsw.in/steel/about-us>
- Ziolo, M., Bąk, I., & Cheba, K. (2020). THE ROLE OF SUSTAINABLE FINANCE IN ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS: DOES IT WORK? Technological and Economic Development of Economy, 27(1), 45–70. <https://doi.org/10.3846/tede.2020.13863>